

CONTENT OF LITERARY EDUCATION IN BEGINNER CLASSES

Pulatova Nasiba Baydillayevna

Master's degree at Jizzakh State Pedagogical University "Theory and methodology of Education and training (Primary Education)"

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Annotation: this article discusses and analyzes the theoretical and practical significance of the study of literary theoretical concepts in the elementary grades.

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It is known that the role of fiction in the education of the younger generation spiritually healthy on the basis of national values, in the formation of personality is incomparable. But progressing aspects that can positively affect the reader's personality in a work of art, life and artistic truths reflected in the text, finding those that serve to clear their heart, and instilling in their nature is not an easy process in the person in whom it is being formed. In the educational system, when carrying out such complex and responsible work, there is a need for a subject known as the "method of teaching literature" and a well-versed teacher who loves his profession. This textbook "methodology for teaching literature in primary classes" is a beacon-level guide that shows both scientific and theoretical and practical aspects of teaching literature on the example of reading lessons to students of pedagogical faculties of higher education institutions, that is, teachers of the future primary class. In it, an attempt was made to cover the knowledge necessary to organize reading lessons in a purposeful way, as efficiently as possible, in the system of primary classes, the initial boom of compulsory education. From this purpose, it was decided to present in the textbook the lessons of work on a number of artistic works belonging to the pen of famous representatives of children's literature.

Until future primary school teachers have knowledge and an idea of what, how, in their practical activities, they need to teach their pupils, to learn the ways of their organization in practical activities. If each teacher is able to use even small students on them as if they were in a continuous pattern, children will also gradually get used to it, and in them the desired skill is formed in working with works of art.

As a result, a person of thought is formed in the person of the child. An opinion person will never blindly follow others, will think quietly when it is necessary to react. The teacher I a person who I called to shape in children. To do this, first, he himself must have acquired such qualities. The teacher cannot give what he does not have to his student.

The methodology of teaching literature in primary classes the content of the educational science includes teaching methods, methods, forms and their peculiarities, theoretical and didactic additions related to the work of art, knowledge related to the ways of organizing the activities of a teacher and a student in the process of working with a literary text.

A number of specific principles of organizing literary education on the example of elementary classes reading lessons may be that the command to achieve efficiency in the work of teaching literature at any educational stage without mastering them is perfect. First you need to get into the essence of the concept of the principle of Education.

- the most important system of rules and views, which is relied on in the organization of educational night. Principles pedagogical practice arose as a result of the need for proper organization. Principles are a set of requirements for the teaching process. The main principles of education in the training night are as follows:

- developmental and educational principle of Education;
- the principle of the connection of education with life;
- the principle of learning;
- the principle of systematicity and consistency of Education;
- educational and maturing principle of Education;
- instructional principle of Education:
- the principle of communalism in which education relies on the personality of students;
- the principle of intelligibility of the knowledge given;
- the principle of thoroughness of mastered knowledge;
- the principle of student awareness and creative activity under the guidance of a teacher;
- the principle of growing students ' theoretical thinking skills;
- the principle of the upbringing to have solid knowledge, etc.

At each stage of the educational process, these principles must be observed. But to the content of objects. Depending on the age characteristics of the reader, the availability of instruction manuals, the ratio and content of the principles change to some extent. For example, when the principle of specificity is associated with the organization of observations of natural phenomena, flora and fauna in the process of teaching natural science, when teaching a native language or a foreign language, it will consist in showing grammatical tables, drawing drawings, etc. But in a lively observation in the teaching of any educational subject, that is, a certain perception of something and phenomenon. to follow the principles of thinking. understanding and knowing theoretical conclusions. it is necessary to be able to apply them in experience, in life.

In the process of working on works of art at any stage of education, it is necessary to educate the reader as the owner of noble spiritual qualities. The following special principles of literary education are of paramount importance in the proper organization of classes in this area:

The principle of changing the order of the lesson: according to it, the lessons are in a traditional way, that is, the organizational part, asking for homework and strengthening it, a new lesson statement and strengthening it. it is not carried out in the way of giving a task to the House. While the course process is being worked on some work of art presented in the program, the previous knowledge of the students. to ask controversial controversial questions, relying on their life experiences. it is organized on the basis of creating problem situations and ensuring independent exacerbations of students. The process uses a variety of educational techniques while avoiding repetitions of homogeneity. Homework is given in a way that requires students to think independently and work creatively.

The principle of the relationship of the analysis of works of art with life: ensuring the connection of classes with life in traditional education is the task of the teacher. And in classes aimed at ensuring the spiritual maturation of the student, the interpretation of life phenomena is mastered by the students themselves as part of the analysis of works of art. The teacher guides this process with referrer questions and tasks. There are theoretical concepts that the perception of being is clarified and deepened with volumetric. Readers will learn to find the basis of the personality of literary heroes and all sorts of phenomena that they

themselves may encounter in the air, with the analysis of what is expressed in the work. They respect the scientific and vital truths they find. The full-fledged connection of any literary education with life requires continuity between the organizational aspects of teaching and the selected methods it is advisable to achieve their connection with life and existing natural laws, without bringing various artificial methods and methods into the practice of the educational system.

Let the student apply the knowledge learned in the lesson in life or draw scientific conclusions on his own strength in the lesson on the basis of what he sees in the air. Only then is the knowledge given not only in the memory of the reader, but also in his thinking and psyche, becoming his property of the mind. Hearing something at school, a student who sees something else in life loses confidence in the truths instilled in the lessons. The most correct way is to educate on the basis of life truths. No matter how bitter, complex and unpleasant the truth is, it is useful. It reveals the true nature of life to the person who is eventually forming. Allows him to choose the right way to overcome the difficulties of life.

The principle of motivating the student to independent activities in literary education: this principle of the correct Organization of literary education at each stage of teaching is to work on artistic texts in lessons. the request for homework is in hand when doing all kinds of independent work in a gross or group manner. Mastering a new topic should also be achieved by students as part of the independent implementation of tasks, that is, working on their own. Independent works are presented in a creative or semi-creative way. Short - term independent work performed in 3-4 minutes also activates students. In its nature, it forms the qualities of independent thinking and free activity.

The principle of individualization of teaching literature: the process of school literature lessons. he argues that individualization, regardless of the stage in which education takes place, causes non-letting there be a gap in the acquisition of knowledge. As you know, each creation of God is to some extent different from each other in its intellectual capacity, ability and talent. Each student in the class has a different verb. The basis of this principle is to work with each of the students to the maximum individually. When working separately with a student, his individual characteristics, originality in mastering knowledge, memory, level of mastering, character and interests must necessarily be taken into account.

In literary education, the principle of the priority of the personality of the student: for today's national pedagogy, it is important that those brought up become a pure volunteer, a person prone to spiritual good. This, in turn, is a guarantee that they will be formed as good specialists. It is also a requirement of the period for the growing generation to become an educated and competent specialist, as well as the owner of a healthy spirituality. As you know, each student in the class is unique in its nature, talent, ability, interests and capabilities. None of them exactly repeat the other. Therefore, in the organization of literary education, it is advisable to give tasks taking into account the specific abilities and capabilities of each student, as well as to establish an individual request for knowledge. So that the immense ability given to some student may not be a fruitless sacrifice. a moderately talented second student, on the other hand, will not be able to cope with the task beyond his means and lose confidence.

Pedagogical cooperation in elementary literary education also implies the collective assimilation of knowledge, and its main goal is the formation of an independent, figurative

thinking of participants based on emotions. ensuring direct participation in the assimilation of knowledge, solving complex didactic-creative issues from this surreal method.

When Elementary literary education is organized in cooperation, attention in the study of knowledge as a subject is focused not only on a particular student, but also on a group of students - subjects. In this position, the teacher and the student or group of students enter into a mutual subject-subject relationship. In this process, guidance is carried out in the image of the teacher, and in the activities of students, research is carried out together. As a result of emotional figurative discussion and choice, a strong interpersonal joint action arises. the developed strict requirements for cooperation form the basis for its correct implementation in the educational process. The use of this complex and advanced technology in the direction of the goal pursued in the organization of elementary classes reading classes requires a high level of knowledge, pedagogical training, skill and dedication from the teacher. If the educator lacks any of these aspects or is perceived as lacking in some aspect, it is also not for nothing that the process in question has an opposite effect on learning activities.

Another of the peculiarities of organizing the literary education of primary classes on the basis of pedagogical cooperation is different nature, worldview. it is to be able to realize all the characteristics of subjects with talent and opportunity. Early approaches in this area show that pedagogical cooperation covers open didactic situations, its components and a complex educational process. To date, the cooperation in the process of elementary classes reading lessons is manifested as a progressive idea that develops education. After all, pedagogical approaches, which have a strong point of view on the basis of the concept of pedagogical cooperation, theories, laws and pedagogical systems are united together.

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